

Students and Employment Data using Aadhar and GST

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Abstract:- Efficient policymaking by any government is the cornerstone of good governance. The reliable and timely public data leads to efficient policy and to design and implement programmes effectively. Good policy decisions lead to solving problems like inflation, unemployment, quality education, economic growth etc. However, policymaking is facing twin challenges in collating timely and reliable public data. Among the emerging economies, India is trying hard for one decade to have relatively robust public data through different methods and surveys. However, errors are continuing and they are higher than in higher-income countries.

The same situation is continuing in education and employment data collection also. It is well-known fact that education and Employment data play important role in any country's economic prosperity. Even though the Indian Government is collecting education and employment data through different sources, there is no single agency to verify the reliability of the data collected.

Here an easy and efficient proposal is proposed in this paper to collect student and employment data using Aadhaar and GST numbers. However the government has to develop a portal based on the ideas presented in this paper. by developing a portal for the government. This idea is simple and provides 100% accurate timely data. The proposed method is so flexible, the government can get more and more information by introducing new fields in the database of the portal.

Keywords:- Student data, employees data, Aadhaar, GST, portal.

I. INTRODUCTION

All the Governments in the world concentrate on their countries' economic growth. If their economy grows, employment opportunities and their country's prosperity increase¹. Many studies show that the increase in employability is directly proportional to the quality of education. Education provides skills, efficiency, and development ability in an individual which leads to the availability of qualified employees and increases employment opportunities². Hence the education sector and the employability sector are interrelated.

The quality of education and better employability can be achieved only if the governments make good policies. The government can make good policies only if they have relevant and reliable data on these two sectors.

Indian National Education Policy³says that "better data can improve education in India. If data can be used effectively, the government can build a stronger education system. Data can help decision-makers to allocate resources efficiently. Similarly, accurate data is helpful to the government to make necessary changes in program design, and operational decisions and also in turn helps to review and monitor.

Similarly, the government also need employment data for making recruitment policy, labour policy, etc. Macroeconomic policymaking and analysis are based on employment data.

Normally the educational data and employment data will be collected separately by the Indian government through different departments, and the reliability of the data collected is at stake. So far, no agency is there to check the reliability of data.

In this paper, the author proposed a simple method to collect the higher education student data and employment data of India through a single portal using student Aadhar numbers and GST numbers of business establishments. This facilitates 100% accuracy of data. However, here the main thrust is given only to get the number of students in their final year of study in higher education in our country and student placement data. The advantage of this method is that the entire data can be collected in the electronic mode without using any paper. This method is so flexible that any more data fields can be added to both the student and employment data.

II. PRESENT STUDENT DATA COLLECTION METHOD IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The existing system of collecting educational data in higher education was initiated in 2011 by the All India Survey Of Higher Education (AISHE)⁴. Here also electronic mode is followed without using any paper. The results are presented in the form of the All India survey of higher education (AISHE).

The survey was of utmost necessity as none of the sources of data on Higher Education was giving a complete picture of Higher Education in the country before 2011. For the first time, all the major Stakeholders in Higher Education such as University Grants Commissions, the All

India Council for Technical Education, the Medical Council of India as well as State Governments participated in the data collection exercise.

As per the AISHE report 2019-20⁵, the survey intended to cover all the Institutions in the country engaged in imparting Higher Education (1043 Universities, 42343 colleges, and 11,779 standalone institutes). However, it is sad that some universities and institutions have not participated in this data collection. Data is being collected on several parameters such as teachers, student enrolment, programs, examination results, education finance, infrastructure, etc. Indicators of educational development such as Institution Density, Gross Enrolment Ratio, Pupil-Teacher Ratio, Gender Parity Index, etc. are calculated from the data collected through AISHE.

These are useful in making policy decisions and research for the development of the education sector. The survey is being conducted on annual basis. It is pertinent to mention that the results published in this report are based on the number of institutions that have registered and uploaded their information in specially designed Data Capture Formats (DCFs)⁶. Thus, there is a possibility that all Institutions of Higher Education may not have registered for AISHE 2019-20. This data is purely giving only students' academic information and do not give any idea like placement details, students becoming entrepreneur, etc.

The AISHE report purely depends on the data submitted by each institution. **So far nobody verified the correctness of the data submitted by each educational institution.**

The government may be using some more methods to collect student data. Despite a lot of energy and investment that has gone into building educational data, there remain several methodological and administrative deficiencies, resulting in unreliable or inadequate data.

III. PRESENT EMPLOYMENT DATA COLLECTION METHOD:

Two major sources of data on workforce and employment are the decennial population census and the nationwide quinquennial (5-yearly) surveys by the national sample survey office (NSSO)⁷. The quinquennial survey of NSSO provides data upto 2011-12 only. Hence it was replaced by the periodic labour force survey (PLFS)⁸, which was started in 2017-18 on an annual basis.

Most of the survey on this subject is by the Labour department, the employment exchanges, etc. Our country needs high-frequency data for jobs policy. The labour ministry has started the quarterly survey of employment data from firms' perspective, which can be a critical input for macroeconomic policymaking. Normally these surveys give data on the state of employment in the organized sector. However, here also so much has to be done to have accurate and reliable data.

IV. SUGGESTED PROPOSAL TO COLLECT STUDENT DATA USING AADHAR:

According to Wikipedia⁹, Aadhar is a 12-digit unique identity number that can be obtained voluntarily by the citizens of India and resident foreign nationals who have spent over 182 days in twelve months immediately preceding the date of application for enrolment, based on their biometric and demographic data. The data is collected by the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI), a statutory authority established in January 2009 by the Government of India, under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, following the provisions of the Aadhaar (Targeted Delivery of Financial and other Subsidies, benefits, and services) Act, 2016¹⁰. The Aadhaar number assigned to a resident can be verifiable online anywhere, anytime using the Aadhaar authentication platform. Aadhaar authentication responds only with a yes/no answer.

No resident can have a duplicate Aadhaar number since it is linked to their biometrics, thereby identifying fake and ghost identities. Since duplicates are not possible for the residents, the government is using Aadhaar identification in many areas for the benefit of the people of India. Some of the benefits of Aadhaar are¹¹:

- Agencies and services can contact the central Unique Identification database from anywhere in the country to authenticate a beneficiary's identity by availing of authentication services.
- All the residents can have an identity as Aadhaar and from which they can get other identification documents.
- The UID-enabled-Bank-Account network will offer a secure and low-cost platform to directly remit benefits to residents without the heavy costs associated today with benefit distribution.
- Improved services through increased transparency: Clear accountability and transparent monitoring would significantly improve access and quality of entitlements to beneficiaries and the agency alike.
- Using Aadhaar as an authentication mechanism, residents should be able to access up-to-date information about their entitlements, demand services, and redress their grievances directly from their mobile phones, kiosks, or other means.
- All income tax PAN card holders are linked with Aadhaar.
- Educational institutes are using Student's Aadhaar for recording Bio-Metric attendance.
- Governments are using Aadhaar to extend student benefit schemes like MANA BADI. AMMA VODI in Andhra Pradesh.

At present, almost all the citizens of the country irrespective of age are having Aadhaar numbers that do not have duplicates. Hence this Aadhaar number is included in the proposed database. The basic fields required to collect the final year student's data are given below. However, the government has to develop a portal to store the data submitted by educational institutes.

As this paper is mainly concentrating on the unification of the final year student data and their employment details (if appointed during the campus drive or later in any business establishment), only a limited number of fields are mentioned. More fields can be added at the time of development of the portal by the government as per their additional requirement. The fields to be uploaded by the educational institutes are

- Name of the student as per his Aadhaar card.
- Name of the student as per Xth class certificate.
- Student Aadhaar number
- Year and month in which the student is appearing for the final year of his examination.
- Male/female
- Student mobile number
- Nationality
- Any reservation
- Name of the institute where the student is studying
- Address of the institute where the student is studying with the pin code number.
- Address of the uploading institute with the pin code number.
- State where the institute is located
- Name of the course studying
- Group or main subject of study
- Date of birth

The educational institutions authorized to issue degrees/certificates are only to upload student data. If the institute is affiliated, then affiliating institutes should upload the data of its all affiliated institutes also along with its data. The government may fix the last date to upload the data in the portal. The government may provide a link and a format to the institutes to upload the data. All this process may be made compulsory.

V. PROPOSAL TO COLLECT EMPLOYMENT DATA USING AADHAR AND GST:

GST is an indirect tax that has replaced many indirect taxes in India. The Goods and Service Tax was passed in the parliament on 29th March 2017¹². The Act came into effect on 1st July 2017. GST is one indirect tax for the entire country. All the business establishments in India should have a GST number¹³ if their turnover exceeds 20 lacks in a financial year and 10 lacks for some special category states. GST is applicable in the following:

- Compulsory registration if the turnover exceeds 20 lakh rupees in a financial year.
- To any person making an inter-state taxable supply of goods and /or services.
- Every e-commerce operator
- Supplier of goods and /or services, other than branded services, through e-commerce operator.
- Aggregators who supply services under their brand name
- Casual taxable person
- Non-resident taxable person
- The person required to deduct/collect tax (TDS/TCS).
- Input service distributor

- Supplier of online information and database access or retrieval services from a place outside India to a person in India, other than a registered taxable person.
- The person is required to pay tax under reverse charge.
- Person supplying the goods on behalf of other taxable people (eg. Agent).

However, GST does not apply to some goods, especially to Agriculture. At present, there are more than 1,40,00,000 assesses of GST in our country. The majority of the organized sector employees are working in these establishments only.

The following fields should be included in the above-proposed portal to get the employment data. All the GST-registered establishments should upload the following data either monthly/quarterly/half yearly/yearly as prescribed by the government.

- Name of the organization as appearing in GST data.
- Address of the organization with pin code no
- State
- GST NUMBER
- Name of their employee as per Aadhaar card
- Aadhaar number of the employee
- Designation of the employee
- Date of Joining
- Salary particulars

VI. GOVERNMENT'S ROLE IN GETTING THE ABOVE STUDENT AND EMPLOYMENT DATA:

The Union Government should develop a portal with the fields mentioned above and should issue the following circulars to the concerned departments, business establishments, and educational institutes directing them to upload the data as per the formats given by the Government into the portal and should make it mandatory.

- To direct all the certificate/degree issuing educational authorities to upload the student data in the proposed portal every year before the students appear for their final year examination along with the data of all its affiliated institutes. The government may fix the last date to submit the data.
- To direct all the business establishments to upload the data into the proposed portal as per the frequency (monthly/quarterly/half yearly/yearly) fixed by the government.

VII. ADVANTAGES

The portal proposed is having the student data and employment data, and the Aadhar number links these data. The advantages are

- The government will get the exact number of students who appeared or came out from the colleges
- The government will get an exact number of students placed in different organizations.
- The government will get an exact number of students coming out from each university/certificate issuing authority institution.

- The government will get the exact number of students coming out from each course and the demand for each course.
- The government will get the exact number of students studying in India coming from abroad.
- The government will get the exact number of boys and girls coming from education each year.
- The government will get the exact number of students coming out from each branch or specialization, thereby can assess the demand for each specialization.
- The government can add any number of fields very easily thereby getting the exact information.
- The government can add bank details to the tables and can get the data about self-employment of students' details.

VIII. TECHNOLOGY

The author used RDBMS concepts to create the necessary database and used SQL concepts to communicate with the database. Dummy students and GST data were used to verify the database and results. 100% accurate results yielded. The technical details are not presented in this paper as the government has to develop a separate portal using the ideas presented in this paper.

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